

God's View of Time—A Scientific Outlook

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Abstract

We live in and with time and even know the value of time, but never go deep into time. We all and everything are moving forward with time riding on it like a horse ride. When one retires from life, time stops to that person only, but never stops its own flow. Though countdown starts since inception, but actually time starts just after birth and stop its journey in death. In earth bound time a life extends this much. Time waits for none; it goes on and on days after days, year after year and cycle after cycle. This single arrow-like dimension pulls all 3-D objects, living or non-living, towards a destination. Our existence is based on the time scale in packs of minutes, hours, days and years through moments. In Brahma Kumaris Organization, every day we listen to the Godly Versions or Murlis and try to consume the preferred points. Each word of the Murli is thought to be a gem and every sentence is treated to be a garland made of gems. Some points are extraordinary and sometimes miraculous, some are above the ordinary thoughts which need further scientific explanation. Time is such a point about which God says through Murli that it takes just a second to accomplish many activities i.e., time taken by the human soul to leave one body and to enter into the foetus already implanted within the womb of a mother, to go to the soul world in meditation, to get liberation, to attain

karmateet stage, transformation of Brahma into Vishnu etc. The present paper is actually to highlight time and to feel why God Shiva limits the time just in a second for major attainments? This paper provides an explanation of time in God's view with respect to the earth-bound time as well as time at the speed of light. No other signal can travel faster than light; whereas, the thoughts created in the human mind are not confined to any speed limit and thus it is called superluminal. In our practical life, God's view of time works in a number of ways, for example, telepathic connections through which a mother could know the problem of her infant before it happens or visualizing the difficulty of her son or daughter staying in a long-distant place, spouses catching the frequencies of one another in case of deep relations and Yogis could catch the vibration of others from a long distance. This study reveals the capacity of soul while playing its role within the body and outside the body while departing. In Hinduism, the custom of death ceremony or Shradh is observed after 13 days because the soul takes 13 days time to enter into a mother's womb after leaving the body due to death.

Keywords: Murli versions, Time, Space-time, Superluminal, Tachyonic speed, Quantum measurement, Linear Time-cycle, Soul, Meditation, After-death ceremony, Telepathy.

1. Introduction

Time is to be defined by measuring our experiences of space in between the two events. The feeling of passing time is due to our experience of change in a series of events. Speed and number of events are very much linked with time. It may also be expressed in the way where events are to be serially arranged from the past to the future through the present. Present day time is supposed to move very fast in comparison to the earlier days due to increase of the speed along with the number of events. Whenever we participate in those events, time seems to move faster. Time is treated to be the fourth dimension and intimately associated with three other physical dimensions in space. Time is supposed to be the shelf what keeps the things apart and thus prevents all the things happening at once. Events origin from thoughts and they remain stored in momentary units. Time is calculated longer or shorter depending on the number of moments. When mind is under control, time passes smoothly and the person maintains a good temperament. Speed of mind depends upon the number of thoughts in unit time. Mind slows down in a smaller number of thoughts and hence speed brake is necessary to slow down the mind and to enjoy time in a relaxing mood. Though there is a time limit in any event, but time has no limit without events. Thoughts and consciousness do not occupy any space and hence cannot be destroyed by time.